

Condensation of *p*-Bromophenylacetic acid with Aldehydes Part II

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p-Bromophenylacetic acid has been condensed with *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde, 3:5-dibromo salicylaldehyde. Maximum yields obtained were 58.2%, 85.0%, 99.2% and 99.9% respectively. Phenylacetic acid has also been condensed with 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde and 3:5 dibromo-salicylaldehyde. Maximum yields obtained were 94.9% and 99.8% respectively. The quantitative yields obtained in the presence of a mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine may well be due to the fact that the condensed product might be formed by the intramolecular as well as by intermolecular mechanism suggested by M. Crawford and J.A. Shaw for some similar reactions.

The results of condensation of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid with some substituted benzaldehydes were reported earlier. Some more aldehydes have now been tried. This series of experiments is a continuation of some earlier work^{1,2} designed to study the influence of substituents in Knoevenagel's reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of p-bromophenylacetic acid:—*p*-Bromophenylacetic acid was prepared by the following series of reactions.

Preparation of 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde and 3:5-dibromo-salicylaldehyde. These were prepared by bromination of salicylaldehyde as reported earlier.

Condensation of p-bromophenylacetic acid with p-hydroxy benzaldehyde: Equimolecular quantities of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid (0.21 gm) and aldehyde (0.12 gm) were heated in a 50 ml round bottom flask fitted with reflux condenser at different temperatures, viz., 100, 120, 140 and 150° for different durations of time, viz., 6, 12 and 18 hours in the presence of different bases, viz., pyridine, piperidine, α -picoline, pyridine and acetic anhydride and triethylamine and acetic anhydride. The resulting mass in each case was treated with 10%

1—3. Vishnu Chandra and V. B. Srivastava, communicated for publication in *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.* (in press).

Sodium-bicarbonate solution and the solution was filtered off. The residue, which was neutral, was recrystallised from alcohol and water. It was found to be 4-bromo-4'-hydroxy-stilbene on the basis of its (M.P. 186°), bromine percentage (Found 28.59, $C_{14}H_{11}BrO$ requires 29.06). Maximum yield of 58.2% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140° for 12 hours in the presence of piperidine.

Condensation of p-bromophenylacetic acid with salicylaldehyde: Temperatures tried were 100, 120 and 150° and the duration of heating was 6, 12 and 18 hours. The product was found to be 3-(p-bromophenyl)-coumarin on the basis of its M.P. 189-91° (Reported M.P. 192°), bromine percentage (Found 26.60, $C_{15}H_9BrO_2$ requires 26.53%). Maximum yield of 95% of the resulting product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 150° for 12 hours with a mixture of pyridine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops).

Condensation of p-bromophenylacetic acid with 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde: The temperatures tried were 100, 120 and 145° and the duration of heating was 3, 6 and 12 hours. The product was found to be 3-(p-bromophenyl)-6-bromo-coumarin (M.P. 194-5°), on the basis of its bromine percentage (Found 42.10, $C_{15}H_9Br_2O_2$ requires 42.05). Maximum yield of 99.2% of coumarin was obtained when the reactants were heated with traces of pyridine and acetic anhydride (2 drops pyridine and 3 drops acetic anhydride) at 145° for 3 hours.

TABLE I

S.No.	X	X'	X''	X'''	Y	t	T	A:B	%Yield	M.P. (t ₁)Z
1.	OH	H	H	H	Br	140	12	1:1	58.2	186 ^a Piperidine
2.	H	OH	H	H	Br	150	12	1:1	95.0	189-91 ^b Pyridine+Ac ₂ O
3.	H	OH	H	Br	Br	145	3	1:1	99.2	194-5 ^b Pyridine+Ac ₂ O
4.	H	OH	Br	Br	Br	150	6	1:1	99.9	258 ^b Pyridine+Ac ₂ O
5.	H	OH	H	Br	H	145	6	1:1	94.9	171-2 ^b Pyridine+Ac ₂ O
6.	H	OH	Br	Br	H	145	6	1:1	99.8	185-7 ^b Pyridine+Ac ₂ O

a = 4-Bromo 4'-hydroxy-stilbene; b = coumarins; t = temperature of oil bath in centigrade; T = time in hours; t₁ = melting point in centigrade and Z = bases used.

Condensation of p-bromophenylacetic acid with 3:5 dibromo-salicylaldehyde: The product was found to be 6:8-dibromo-3-(*p*-bromophenyl)-coumarin (M. P. 258°) on the basis of its bromine percentage (Found 52.10, C₁₃H₇Br₃O₂ requires 52.20). Maximum yield of 99.9% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 150° for 6 hours in the presence of pyridine and acetic anhydride.

Condensation of phenylacetic acid with 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde:—Maximum yield of 94.9% of 6-bromo-3-phenyl coumarin (M.P. 170—1°), bromine percentage (Found 26.20, C₁₃H₉BrO₂ requires 26.53%) was obtained by heating the reactants at 140° for 6 hours in the presence of pyridine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops).

Condensation of phenylacetic acid with 3:5-dibromo-salicylaldehyde: Maximum yield of 90.8% of 6:8-dibromo-3-phenyl coumarin (M.P. 185-7°), bromine percentage (Found 42.30, C₁₃H₇Br₂O₂ requires 42.05), was obtained when the reactants were heated at 145° for 6 hours in the presence of pyridine (2 drops) and acetic anhydride (3 drops).

DISCUSSION

In an earlier investigation, the condensation of phenylacetic acid, and *p*-chloro and *p*-bromophenylacetic acid with substituted benzaldehydes, in the presence of traces of different bases, was studied. It was found that the reaction was facilitated by the introduction of halogen atoms like chlorine and bromine in *para*-position in phenylacetic acid and electron releasing groups in *ortho* or *para*-position in benzaldehyde. The reaction was hindered by the introduction of electron attracting groups in the *ortho* or *para*-position in benzaldehyde. The present investigation deals with the condensation of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid with substituted hydroxy benzaldehydes in the presence of different bases. This series of experiments was carried out to study the influence of hydroxy group alone as well as in the presence of halogen substituents on the aldehyde component. As Knoevenagel's reaction involves the carbanion addition to the carbonyl group, the reaction is facilitated by the introduction of electron releasing groups like hydroxy group in *ortho* or *para*-position of benzaldehyde. It was found that a maximum yield of 58.2% of stilbene was obtained in the condensation of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid with *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde in the presence of traces of piperidine, while with *o*-hydroxy benzaldehyde, the yield was only 28.0% in the presence of traces of piperidine. The yield was, however, found to be quantitative when *o*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and *p*-bromophenylacetic acid were heated at 145° for 12 hours in the presence of traces of pyridine and acetic anhydride. This result obviously indicates that the mechanism of the reaction in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride is different from the classical mechanism. M. Crawford and J. A. M. Shaw⁵ have suggested a mechanism for a similar reaction in the presence of a mixture of sodium salt of carboxylic acid and acid anhydride. In the present case, the base is pyridine instead of the carboxylate ion. The following scheme based on Crawford's mechanism can be tentatively proposed to explain the quantitative yields obtained in the reaction of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid and salicylaldehyde.

4. Ng. Ph. Bui. Hoi, Ng. Hoan and M. R. Khenisoi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, Part III, (1951) 2907.

5. M. Crawford and J. A. M. Shaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, Part III, (1953) 3435.

where $\text{R} = \text{p-BrC}_6\text{H}_4-$

The above mechanism suggests that in the presence of acetic anhydride, the coumarin is formed by intermolecular (VII $\rightarrow$ VIII $\rightarrow$ IX $\rightarrow$ X) as well as by intramolecular (VII $\rightarrow$ VIII $\rightarrow$ XI $\rightarrow$ XII $\rightarrow$ XIII $\rightarrow$ X) mechanism. In absence of acetic anhydride, the coumarin is formed by the usual mechanism only and so the yield should not be as high as when acetic anhydride is also present.

p-substituted benzaldehydes should be more reactive than ortho-substituted benzaldehydes on account of steric hindrance offered by the ortho-substituent. This has been found to be the case. The maximum yield in the condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with *p*-bromophenylacetic acid was found to be 58.2% while with *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, it was only 28.0%. As expected the yields in the condensation of *p*-bromophenylacetic acid with bromo salicylaldehydes were found to be greater than those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes.

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